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IN2CCAM Project: Objectives, Innovation, Methodology and Implementation

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Abstract This paper presents the objectives and methodology of IN2CCAM project that proposes to develop, implement, and demonstrate innovative technologies and services for infrastructures and users to include connected and automated vehicles in the transport of passengers and goods. The goal is providing benefits to all citizens by implementing a full integration of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) services in the transport system. Cars, small buses, and trucks without driver will intend to remedy human errors with great impact for society: i) safety (i.e., reducing the number of road accidents caused by human error; ii) environment (i.e., reducing transport emissions and congestion by smoothing traffic flow and avoiding unnecessary trips); iii) inclusiveness (i.e., ensuring inclusive mobility and good access for all as elderly or disabled people with physical problems). The approach is based on the implementation and integration of enhanced Physical, Digital and Operational Infrastructures to enrich CCAM services and increase safety and traffic efficiency.

Keywords:

Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility, ICT platform, ICT tools, EV services

1 Introduction

Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) is expected to reshape the way of travelling and moving in Europe and around the world [1]. By the CCAM, the automated vehicles have to be integrated into the mobility and transport system by designing and implementing infrastructures, new services, platforms, cooperation and governance models. Fully automated driving will double existing average road infrastructure capacity by smoothing traffic flow, by enabling off-peak usage of infrastructure for freight transportation.

In December 2019, the European Commission announced a comprehensive and ambitious strategy package for Europe to become the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050 [2]. In the mobility sector a basic importance is given to the digitalisation of transport focusing on automated mobility. To this aim the European Union is placing big effort for accelerating the deployment of CCAM innovative technologies and services, aiming to exploit the full benefits generated by automation (e.g. increased safety and reduced environmental impact) [3].

Smart traffic management will further increase efficiency and reduce congestion. CCAM enabled

shared mobility services will allow seamless integration with public transport and Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) platforms. It will provide accessible mobility to people who cannot drive (e.g. incapacitated or disabled people, and those without a driving license), or who no longer want to drive [4].

Concerning freight and logistics, the shortage of truck drivers, specifically for the long haul, and the demand for better working conditions requires higher levels of automation that could support further transport productivity [5]. According to the European Transport Workers Federation and the International Road Union, a driver shortage of 21% exists across the freight transport sector. Moreover, CCAM coupled with innovative fleet management may enable larger quantities of freight to be transported compared with current operating practice and guarantee the same transit time even at lower speeds (i.e., saving energy) [6].

In the recent years, the research and innovation areas focus on CCAM topics and services for managing and controlling autonomous driving systems. Some novel contributions enlighten that the most modern technologies based on Information and communications technologies, such as Connected and Cooperative Services, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data allow to connect users, vehicles and infrastructures in an intelligent, efficient, safe and sustainable manner [7, 8]. Moreover, Machine Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms architectures are used for performing the following different tasks: motion planning, vehicle localization, pedestrian detection, traffic sign detection, roadmarking detection, automated parking, vehicle cybersecurity and fault diagnosis [9, 10]. Although the research in the CCAM service area is very effective, the real application of the proposed technologies needs to be further pursued.

To this aim, the project IN2CCAM will help to develop new mobility concepts for passengers and goods - leading to healthier, safer, more accessible, sustainable, cost-effective and demand-responsive transport everywhere. Therefore, the IN2CCAM innovation is based on the three pillars affecting safety and resilience: technologies, regulations and human factors (individual and organisational aspects).

IN2CCAM will propose and implement a set of physical, digital and operational solutions in 4 Lead Living Labs (LLs) and 2 Follower LLs complexively in 5 different countries (Finland, Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal).

In order to present IN2CCAM project, the present paper is structured as follows: Chapter 1 describes the objectives and ambition of the project; Chapter 2 hangs out the methodology used to achieve the project objectives and the progresses it pursue ; Chapter 3 identifies the expected results of the project and Chapter 4 concludes the paper.

2 Objectives and Ambition of IN2CCAM

IN2CCAM deals with the three challenges as follows:

Physical infrastructures (challenge 1): the physical infrastructures in each LLs will be updated so that the autonomous vehicles can travel considering the possibilities of dynamic dedicated lanes, intelligent traffic lights and intelligent road signs.

Digital (intelligent) infrastructures (challenge 2): the digital infrastructures are developed in

IN2CCAM by employing all technologies necessary for enhancing and integrating CCAM in the urban and peri urban road traffic. Figure 1 represents the digital infrastructure built by IN2CCAM. Starting from the traffic management platform existing in the LLs, the traffic management systems are upgraded by the IN2CCAM platform extended server with a high level of automation to support the CCAM solutions.

Operational Infrastructure (challenge 3): The services will be integrated in urban planning and urban economics, with appropriate governance models in order to ensure collaboration between stakeholders. Business models for automated and shared vehicles will be provided, as well as interoperability and integration with public transport.

The Proposed actions should develop and demonstrate concepts of traffic and fleet management to achieve a desirable integration of CCAM vehicles in the entire mobility system.

Figure 1 – Digital Infrastructure of IN2CCAM

In order to foster the advance of the CCAM solutions and prepare them for the deployment in clean, safe, efficient and smart transport, five general objectives support the above overall objective:

Objective 1: Determine the concepts of fleet and traffic management in the CCAM ecosystem considering PDOI in order to optimize the mobility of people and goods.

Objective 2: Design, implement and test the physical, digital infrastructure intermodal interfaces between the platforms of the CCAM ecosystem and the local platforms for fleet and traffic management also by implementing services for the interoperability in multimodal transport systems in different geographic locations.

Objective 3: Design, implement and test advanced simulation and digital twin models in order to assess new traffic management strategies for CCAM.

Objective 4: Design adaptive traffic optimization and flow balancing strategies based on real-time

traffic intensity, prediction of traffic situations in the immediate future and green times adjustment in line with real time traffic volume, involving also users in real time.

Objective 5: Propose, develop and test new effective cooperation, governance and business models for operating CCAM services integrated in the real-life fleet and traffic management systems including the interaction between different transportation modes.

The final goal will be the creation of a targeted symbiosis between the physical, digital and operational infrastructures that will be connected, interoperable and linked each other, with the overall goal of realizing a CCAM in the transport system able to guarantee safety, environment and inclusiveness.

2 IN2CCAM Methodology

The IN2CCAM project aims to design, implement, and integrate the three main challenges: updating new physical infrastructures, using and updating novel digital infrastructures, proposing suitable operational infrastructures. In order to reach such general objectives, the overall methodology of IN2CCAM is based on the definition, organization, implementation and evaluation of a set of LLs that will be the basis for implementing a full integration of CCAM services in the transport system. According to the LL methodology and approach, IN2CCAM will focus the activities on the user and the open innovation ecosystem, operating in 6 territorial contexts and integrating innovation and research processes in a partnership between public and private entities. The concept will be based on a systematic co-creation approach and integrated innovation processes. These processes will be integrated through the co-creation, exploration, experimentation and evaluation of innovative services, scenarios, concepts and related technological solutions in real use cases of CCAM.

These use cases will involve user communities, not only as observing subjects but also as sources of creation. This approach allows all stakeholders to consider both the overall performance of the services and its potential adoption by users. To this aim, IN2CCAM will propose, deploy and demonstrate innovative services, management algorithms and governance models starting from the study and analysis of the described LLs. In particular, the IN2CCAM LLs are divided in two types: Lead LLs (Tampere, Trikala, Turin, Vigo) and follower LLs (Bari and Quadrilatero).

The LL areas have been chosen to represent different European Countries for full integration of CCAM as well as with different user and stakeholder experiences. The proposed demonstrations will be of different types. First, the demonstrations will be operational in real traffic with autonomous vehicles. Second, different types of autonomous vehicles will be contemplated in the real demonstrations integrated in real traffic.

The roles of the Lead LLs will be to implement the new services and the IN2CCAM platform extended server, implement the DTN approach for maintenance and prediction, collect data from the field, evaluate the perception and the reactions of the involved people, provide data and information for the governance models and rules determination.

The roles of the Follower LLs are to follow the results obtained by the Lead LLs and applying their proposed services in the context of LL by implementing simulation campaigns. Hence, the Follower LLs will provide data about the traffic, the maps, the available infrastructures, the traffic rules and any results of experiments in progress about CCAM. This idea of involving Follower LLs is very effective

because is able to amplify the results of the Leader LL and enrich the impact with the experience of different cities, contexts and citizen perceptions.

The overall approach is based on the guidelines of the FESTA European project, thus it is split in three phases: Preparation, Usage and Analysis.

Preparation phase The preparation phase starts by the setting of the basis as regards the traffic and fleet management innovative implementations and deployments. This phase is useful to identify the mobility needs, concerns and requirements of different user groups as well as of different stakeholders (fleet and traffic operators, cities, legislators, service providers).

Usage phase In the usage phase, the new physical, digital and operational infrastructures will be implemented in each Lead LL. To this aim all the systems and services will be verified so that they operate properly in each LL before the demonstrations start. The existing ICT services will be integrated with the deployed new CCAM services and solutions in the Lead LLs and the activities in the demonstration areas will be coordinated to ensure that the users actively participate in the demonstrations and that the needed data are collected. Moreover, the Lead and Follower LLs will provide data and use cases in order to simulate the CCAM ecosystem in large scale by forecasting future results, benefits and barriers.

Analysis phase In the analysis phase, a framework for impact assessment will be set up to measure the performance of the solutions in each LL and their impact on the CCAM ecosystem. Test methods will be proposed and a specific testing environment that includes CCAM simulation tool will be used for testing the interoperability of end-to-end communication by each partner. Moreover, real traffic conditions analysis using advanced simulation models and tools and real-world data will be simulated considering all the LLs.

Using the find of the demonstration, an evidence-based governance framework, business models, policy and regulatory recommendations for a widespread uptake of IN2CCAM innovation will be performed. Specific objectives will be designing an inclusive evidence-based framework for an effective governance of CCAM-enabled traffic and fleet management solutions meeting needs of policy makers, regulatory authorities, service providers and transport operators. In addition, new cost-efficient multi-stakeholder business and operating models will be proposed for an efficient integration of CCAM and fleet and traffic management systems, based on the sharing of both benefits and risks associated with the future operation of the IN2CCAM innovation. The final output will be regulatory and policy recommendations targeted at EU and international decision makers, proposing actions facilitating widespread of the IN2CCAM innovations so as to convince stakeholders to invest in CCAM infrastructure.

2.1 *Digital twin network and AI-based approaches for innovative services*

The Digital twin (DT) technology benefits in many domains, such as real-time system remote monitoring and control and risk assessment. A DT can be defined as an integrated system composed of a physical object, its virtual twin, data, services and connections between them. The virtual twin continually adapts to operational changes based on the collected online data and information and predicts the state of the corresponding physical object. Based on this definition, a DT is an intelligent

and constantly evolving system, which monitors, controls, and optimizes the physical object through its life cycle. DT is the accurate digital replica of a real-world object across multiple granularity levels, and this real-world object could be a device, machine, or an industrial process or a complex physical system such a traffic network including CCAM. IN2CCAM progresses beyond the SOA by implementing a Digital Twin Network (DTN) defined as a many-to-many mapping network constructed by multiple one-to-one DTs (see Fig. 2). In other words, DTN uses advanced communication technologies to realize real-time information interaction between the physical object and its virtual twin, the virtual twin and other virtual twins, and the physical object and other physical objects.

Figure 2 – DTN architecture of IN2CCAM

The proposed DTN realizes the dynamic interaction and synchronized evolution of the multiple physical objects and virtual twins, by using accurate DT modelling, communications, computing and physical data processing technologies. In DTN, physical objects and virtual twins can communicate, collaborate, share information, complete tasks with each other, and form an information sharing network by connecting multiple DT nodes [11]. The DTN can provide better services for drivers in urban lives by utilizing electronic sensor technologies, data transmission technologies, and intelligent control technologies. In particular, the DTN will provide the virtual vision of the transportation system which can help to manage traffic and optimize public transportation service planning efficiency. In addition, DTN will offer new opportunities to maintain transportation facilities, such as sensor and cameras failures. By simulating the usage of transportation facilities in DTN, facilities malfunction can be predicted in advance, which helps to make maintenance decision in an appropriate way. Finally, DTN will be a tool for providing innovative services for transport, such as traffic information reporting, vehicles secure access, and vehicles data sharing. With the potential of implementing

computing-intensive applications, edge computing will be combined with DT to enhance intelligent transportation capabilities including CCAV in the traffic system.

To this aim, in DTN-enabled autonomous driving control, the smart vehicles' running states and perceived environmental information needs to be transmitted to the DTN servers in real time to update the virtual twin model.

To guarantee strict data transmission delay in such vehicular networks with highly dynamic topology, IN2CCAM will secure DTN operation in vehicular networks.

Hence, the DTN models will continuously update using adaptive control or real-time algorithms to perform predictive analysis of accidents and dangerous situations and implement control actions that minimize risks and improve safety [12].

The DT components as well as the optimal control algorithms are implemented at each node of the V2X network. The proposed optimal control algorithms will be based on deep-learning architectures such as deep neural networks (DNN) and deep reinforcement learning (DRL) that produce results comparable to and in some cases surpassing human expert performance. DNN and DRL will be used to define and implement new services and solutions for:

- Real time traffic light management including the control of the approaching of the emergency vehicles
- Real time traffic light management including the control of pedestrian and cyclists
- Optimal Parking management considering users and infrastructures requirements
- End user applications for VRU
- Advanced traffic manager to traffic monitor in real time and provide solutions for the load balancing problems
- CCAV operations for connecting bus lines, pedestrian zones and bicycle routes
- Advanced traffic information system integrating CCAM.

Moreover, the AI techniques use computational agents that learn to make decisions by trial-and-error approaches [13, 14]. Starting from unstructured input data, very large information and system models the AI algorithms propose make decisions and what actions to perform to optimize an objective. The DT, simulation models and collected data in the field will be the inputs of the AI algorithms.

Each service will be implemented starting from a TRL 4/5 and reaching at least a TRL6/7.

3 Expected Results

The main need of the transportation sector is increasing safety, ensuring inclusiveness and reducing environmental impact. The deployment of CCAM innovative technologies and services with the digitalization of transport are key elements to satisfy this need. To this aim IN2CCAM considers addressing three main specific needs: implementation and integration of enhanced Physical, Digital and Operational Infrastructures.

According to the Physical infrastructures need, the autonomous vehicles have to be integrated in the urban and peri-urban traffic in suitable physical infrastructures such as dynamic dedicated lanes, intelligent traffic lights and intelligent road signs. Regarding the Digital infrastructures need, the traffic management systems have to be upgraded by a high level of automation to support the CCAM

solutions and services. Finally, for the Operational infrastructures need the services have to be integrated in urban planning and urban economics, with appropriate governance models in order to ensure collaboration between stakeholders. Business models for automated and shared vehicles have to be provided, as well as interoperability and integration with public transport.

To this end, IN2CCAM targets to achieve four expected results (ER):

ER.1: Designing, implementing and integrating in urban and peri-urban traffic enhanced services for CCAM such as real time traffic light management, optimal parking management , end user applications for VRU, advanced traffic manager for traffic monitoring in real time and traffic load balancing, CCAV operations for connecting tramlines, bus lines, pedestrian zones and bicycle routes, advanced traffic information systems integrating CCAM;

ER.2: Enabling the enhanced CCAM services by innovative technologies (implemented at least at TRL 6/7) such as Artificial Intelligence, Digital Twin Networks, new simulation models and High-Definition Maps;

ER.3: Successful in the field demonstrations in 4 Lead LLs and by simulation in 4 Lead LLs and 2 Follower LLs located in 5 European Countries;

ER.4: Published innovation results in open access journals; Exploitation roadmap entailing replication strategy and policy recommendations, Global leadership of European CCAM, Software and ICT sectors by developing cost-effective and affordable solutions, Innovative HW & SW solutions, technologies, processes, services, equipment, and tools with at least TRL 6/7.

4 Conclusions

This work presents the objectives and future outcomes of IN2CCAM European project that proposes use cases implemented in five European Countries to test different ways to deploy road automation in urban and peri urban applications.

The innovative CCAM-oriented business models will be guided by arbitrations in CCAM technology between the primary interests of VRUs, CAV users and the society as a whole. Novel contract-based business plans guaranteed by Non-Fungible Tokens will be considered as applied to contracts between actors of CCAM services. On the one hand, deployment of CCAM services on a wide scale across European countries requires EU market homogenization, including opening of markets currently restricted, especially in the field of safety such as electronic traffic management. The operation models of CCAM services are strongly influenced by CCAM-specific legislation particular to a country or region and smart cities. The impact of this operation on the business plan will be analyzed to help designing effective business plans for CCAM well adapted to the local area. The operating models of CCAM services will be strongly impacted soon by the availability of disruptive technologies such as digital twins and the development of post-5G technologies and 6G. The impact of these novel technologies will be accounted for in CCAM-oriented business and operating models. In this context IN2CCAM will target both public authorities and service providers to improve synergies between private and public investments to improve the CCAM in urban and peri urban areas. To this aim, the IN2CCAM business models will be based on active and formal collaboration between private service providers with the city authorities. Thus, its business models will be based on and will thus promote

the establishment of contractual public-private partnerships in the interested cities and regions, as this is a main factor for their sustainability and success. Additionally, IN2CCAM will engage a CCAM ecosystem in each LL, as a body representing the views and interests of the relevant manufactures and private and public stakeholders. The CCAM new technologies developed by IN2CCAM will generate new skilled jobs.

CCAM has also a great potential to contribute to key policy goals like the UN Sustainable Development Goals , Vision Zero and the European Green Deal. Reducing transport emissions and congestion by optimising capacity, smoothening traffic flow and avoiding unnecessary trips is a one of the main expected impacts of the services integration in the urban and peri urban transportation. The project development recommendations and guidelines will unlock the deployment of CCAM and will therefore contribute to improve the air quality in urban centres. In particular, the environmental impacts will be monitored and forecast in all the lead LL (by measuring the sustainability indicators during the test). Moreover, the impact of the environmental sustainability will be evaluated by the simulation in all the LL to forecast the future impact of the CCAM when the CCAVs will be in large number and completely integrated in the transport of goods and people.

One of the reasons of the lack of awareness and acceptance by citizens and policy makers of the transition to CCAM mobility is the fact that impacts on safety of the integration of CCAM solutions are not well understood. The IN2CCAM will work to change public opinion by three actions. First, the testing activities and the implementation of the CCAM services in the Lead LLs across Europe will be of great relevance to the validation of safe CCAM functioning. Second, the knowledge and data gathered and collected on the field and by simulation about safety of human driven and autonomous vehicles will provide the impact of the integrated services about the reduction of the number of road fatalities and accidents caused by human error. Third, such data will be analyzed and disseminated both at local level and at scientific levels.

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